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Growth and Development of Used Car Market in India

Dr. K. Natarajan,

Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, DDE., Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar – 608 002, Tamilnadu, India.

Dr. K. Soundararajan,

Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration, DDE., Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar – 608 002, Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract

The used-car business is 1.3 times bigger than the new-car market and growing at a faster rate, almost three million second-hand cars were sold in India last year compared to the 2.5 million new cars. To a large extent, the used-car space is immune to demand fluctuations. The impact of the economy on the used-car industry is more muted than for the new-car industry because in the used-car business, volumes are generated by cars changing hands as well. The slowdown in new-car sales has affected the used-car industry, and growth has slowed from about 22-25 per cent in earlier years to about 18-20 per cent now. However, the market is still undeveloped. A large part of the sales is done through friendship circles, within families or by roadside dealers. The organised sector accounts for only 18 per cent of the market compared to 11 per cent five years ago. This paper discusses the growth and development of the used car market in India and its future.

Keywords: Used car market, automobile sector, Second hand cars, India, Passenger car.

Introduction

In 2013, 865 million passenger cars were in use worldwide, and over 65 million units were produced in the same year. Worldwide, passenger car sales are expected to continue to increase to about 100 million units in 2017. Car sales started falling dramatically during the 2008-2009 economic crisis. Today, India is back to pre-crisis levels. China is ranked as the largest passenger car manufacturer in the world. Not only India is among the most populous countries globally, it is also one of the world's largest markets for automobiles and two-wheelers, trailing only China, the United States, Japan and Germany. Between January and June 2014, about 1.6 million motor vehicles were sold in India, some 1.3 million of which were passenger cars. By 2025, it is expected that about 6.7 million passenger cars will be sold in India. The leading

automakers include Maruti Suzuki, Hyundai Motor and Mahindra & Mahindra. In 2013, Honda emerged as the fastest growing company in the market. The Japanese carmaker's sales are expected to have surged 60 percent in 2014. Passenger vehicles are ranked as the second most important motor vehicle segment in terms of sales. India's automobile industry is one of the fastest growing in the world and it is already the sixth largest globally. According to a SIAM report, annual car sales could reach 5 million vehicles by 2015 and more than 9 million vehicles by 2020.

Major Player in Used Car Market in India

As sales of new cars remain sluggish, the second-hand market is increasingly turning into a welcome source of revenue for car makers. The prudence of having a used-cars division has already been realised by Volkswagen, Ford, Toyota, Hyundai, Maruti Suzuki, and even by luxury car makers BMW, Audi and Mercedes-Benz. The used-car facility helps a company introduce its brand to a customer even when a new car is beyond his reach. According to a Delhi-based analyst, 40-45 per cent of car buyers are below 30, and are looking to upgrade from a two-wheeler to a hatchback or even a sedan. The target customer for a used car comes primarily from this segment. For the country's second-largest car maker, Hyundai Motor, of the 380,253 new cars it sold last year, a significant chunk was to customers who had either owned or driven a used Hyundai car before. Hyundai, which has maintained steady 20 per cent sales growth over the past five years, sold 70,000 used cars last year, many of them to first-time buyers.

Maruti True Value, which was launched way back in 2001 to sell company-owned used cars, has also been a significant contributor to sales of new cars. Its network of 454 outlets across 260 cities helps draw customers from all over the country. More than profits, the idea for any manufacturer is to draw and retain customers from the time he is ready to buy a car. To tap this market, companies offer certified pre-owned cars complete with multi-point scrutiny with attractive discounts and freebies. They also keep a check on the after-sale service. Many used car customers are upgrading to higher-end new car models because of product quality and reliability.

Growth of Used Car Market

Despite the automobile industry witnessed sluggish sales numbers in the last few quarters, the used or pre-owned car segment is growing fast, and is likely to accelerate in future. The used car market, although having been around for some years, has gained traction of late with more players increasing focus on it. With poor sales numbers dogging the industry, the used cars have come to provide succor to several manufacturers and the larger ones have enhanced the services and offerings to capitalise on this segment. Many manufacturers already have flourishing businesses under their own brands — Maruti Suzuki's True Value, Mahindra's First Choice, Tata Motors' Assured and Hyundai's HPromise are very large. In the recent past, big German giants Audi, BMW and Mercedes-Benz also have increased the focus on this segment.

The average ownership of vehicles is now around four years. While the new car market size is 2.5 million, the used car market is about 3 million today. The domestic used car market is growing at 15 per cent and it is expected it to double in the next four years. India has 15,000 used car dealers, of which about 750 are organised. Globally, it is largely unorganised. As with the luxury car segment, which accounts for only around 3 per cent of total car sales, used luxury car sales account for a fraction of the total with entry level cars dominating.

Till about a decade ago, in the absence of organised players, more than 60 percent of all used car sales were C2C (customer to customer) among friends and relatives, with a 'Circle of Trust'. The remaining sales were managed by local unorganised dealers. In 2001, Maruti became the first major organised player to enter the market with the launch of its used car brand – Maruti True Value. Today, the Indian consumer has woken up to the positive value equation of pre-owned cars, and rightfully so. Pre-owned cars give higher flexibility and reach to prospective car owners, whether first-time buyers or repeat, due to the price advantage they offer. The economical prices of pre-owned cars help all types of buyers. Factors responsible for the increasing popularity of used car's are:

- First-time car buyers: Lower price point and wide variety ensure that a used car buyer gets a technologically advanced and wide range of cars at fair prices.
- Second car at economical price: Several Indian families have a need for more than one car and used cars offer them a more economically viable option.
- Upgrade to a bigger car at a lower budget: This is especially true in case of people from Tier 2 cities and towns. A used car allows them the opportunity to upgrade from a two-wheeler to a four-wheeler without stretching their budget.

Other factors responsible for the increasing popularity of used cars are the multitude of quality choices available coupled with an increase in income. All this has created a situation where people want to upgrade their vehicles more frequently. The paradigm shift from buying new cars to used cars can be attributed to the increasing organisation of the pre-owned car players. Apart from these obvious reasons, there are other benefits that make buying a pre-owned car a popular practice, such as lower rate of depreciation, easy finance options, and hassle-free documentation along with clean history.

Current state of used car market in India

According to estimates in the US, for every new car sold, around three used cars are sold. In Europe, this ratio is 1:2, while currently in India it is 1:1.1 and expected to become 1:1.3 by 2015. In Europe and other mature markets, the number of intended new car buyers is increasing, while the number of intended used car buyers is declining. In India, it's a reverse trend that can be attributed to the rising cost of fuel and increasing disposable income. Though the general economic slowdown has hit new car sales numbers, the used cars market has seen an uptrend, clearly indicating that used cars will continue to move forward. There are several reasons for the evolution and subsequent shift and growth of the used car market in India. Among them are:

- **Improved quality:** Used cars available nowadays have an improved and, hence, longer life due to technological advancements.
- **Better maintenance:** Due to improved quality and performance of mechanical parts, today's cars are easier and better to maintain. Even a used car with 40,000-50,000km on the odometer will be much easier to maintain than a car with similar mileage 8-9 years ago.
- **Less usage:** Several urban families have more than one car. And the second or third car is relatively less driven and well kept. These are great used cars to be bought and offer excellent value for money to car buyers.
- **Internet access:** With easy availability to high speed internet, more and more people are able to buy or sell cars on the web. Search costs have also come down, thereby reducing the dependency on word-of-mouth advertising.
- **Reducing dependency on used car dealers:** People did not prefer to sell/buy used cars through self-appointed used car dealers because they could not be sure of the quality as well as the history of the cars sold. Organised players like Carnation buy only 2 of the 10 cars evaluated. This ensures high quality of the used cars sold.
- **Expansion of organised used car players:** With the organised players stepping in, the used cars market has benefited from fair deals, warranties, better retail network, credibility, transparency, easy availability of finances. Carnation provides an assurance that all cars sold through its showrooms are bought by the right people. Hence, both the seller and buyer are assured of their investment. These have all made buying a used car easy. Organised used car showrooms also allow prospective customers to pick and choose cars from various brands and segments.

Even though today less than 20 percent of the used car market is organised, the lack of organised players has not proven to be an obstacle. There is a huge scope for growth as most of the market remains untapped. The growth in used car sales volumes clearly indicates that the growth prospect for used cars is more as compared with that of new cars by 2017. Since the ratio of new versus used cars in India is still 1:1.1, the old car market will grow much faster than the new and within that segment the organised sector will grow the fastest to bring the ratio closer to the 1:3. That's the norm in developed markets.

The future of the used car market

The used car market in India is expected to grow by a CAGR of 20 percent in the next five years, with the organised sector playing a big role in this growth story. At present, there are about 750 organised used car outlets in India. In order to keep up with the projected growth, there is a demand for 3,500-4,000 outlets. Yet another important fact to consider is the likely implementation of GST. There will be uniform tax laws across all states making selling and registration of used cars a simpler and economical process.

The strong domestic growth for new vehicle sales during 2008-12, which witnessed a compounded annual growth rate of 14 per cent, led to an increased inventory of used cars. Several such trade-in cars are refurbished, thoroughly checked and put on sale usually with a warranty by organised players. Strong bargaining skills can fetch a used refurbished car low mileage at less than half its original sticker price. This is because of increased supply led by reduction in the average period owners hang on to their cars. Till a few years ago, people used to keep their car for about five years on average. This has now come down to about three years.

According to estimates, used-car sales in India at 3.22 million vehicles are 1.2 times the sales in the new-car segment. Last year, according to data by the Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers (SIAM), India witnessed sales of 2.68 million units of the new passenger vehicles, including cars, utility vehicles and vans. This ratio is changing further in favour of the used car industry over the next five years. The used car market will be double the size of the new car market by 2018, according to estimates. Several of the used car buyers, according to dealers, are first time car owners as well as those who wish to have a second car in the family.

According to Mahindra First Choice Wheels, 80 per cent of its buyers choose a model from the B or C segment, whereas only five per cent choose the A and A+ segment. The balance comprises the D and E segment. The used car industry is a mirror reflection of the new car market. Maruti Suzuki dominates the used car demand with consumers rushing for proven Maruti Suzuki models such as Wagon R, Swift and Alto and Hyundai models like Santro, i10, i20. For a used car buyer, the quality of the car and the price of the car are the two main things. A second-hand car buyer is not a second class buyer, it could be his first car. The market for used cars in India is huge.

The underlying potential of the used car industry has attracted financial investors as well. Private equity and venture capital fund companies such as Gaja Capital, Premji Invests, IFCI Ventures and Phi Advisors have made investments in MFCW and Carnation Auto. MFCW, which is depending on Mahindra & Mahindra for finance, is contemplating an initial public offering. This is also to provide an exit to the five-year-old PE investor Phi Advisor, which has picked up a 10 per cent stake in the company in 2008 for Rs 80 crore.

Conclusion

India represents one of the world's largest car markets. Easy availability of finance and rising income levels are encouraging the middle class population to upgrade their two wheelers to a car. The automobile industry now expects double-digit growth in sales this fiscal on improving macro-economic sentiments, stable commodity prices, re-start of mining activity and infra projects, and higher industrial activity with an improved investment climate. Auto sales have recovered after a two year gap and the overall yearly performance is likely to improve in FY16. Passenger vehicle sales increased 3.90 percent year-on-year in the fiscal ended March 2015 at 2.6 million units, and SIAM forecasts sales to grow 6 percent to 8 percent this fiscal. Besides,

the growing organized used car market has also been a positive growth factor in the used car market of the country.

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